

ECONOMICAL SITUATION OF FEMALE SCHOOL DROPOUTS IN INDIA

Abstract:

Education is a crucial tool for promoting economic development and social welfare. By empowering individuals with knowledge, skills, and values critical for personal growth and well-being, education contributes to the development of society and the economy. Despite the importance of education, many girls in India are still dropping out of school, significantly impacting the country's economic growth and social welfare. Here, we will explore the effect of female school dropouts on economic growth and social welfare in India.

Keywords:

Female, school, dropouts, India, economical, situation.

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INTRODUCTION

Education and Economic Development

Education plays a critical role in driving economic development. It is a well-established fact that educated individuals are more productive and earn higher wages than those without education. According to a report by the World Bank, a one-year increase in the average years of schooling can increase a country's GDP by 0.37%. Furthermore, educated individuals are more likely to contribute to the growth of industries, as they possess the necessary skills and knowledge required in a particular field.[1,2,3]

The Importance of Education

Education is essential for empowering individuals to improve their financial status, health, and overall well-being. It enables individuals to develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and communication skills necessary for personal and professional growth. Education also promotes social inclusion and equity by providing equal opportunities for all individuals, regardless of their gender, race, or ethnicity.

However, despite the crucial role of education in promoting economic growth and social welfare, many girls in India are still dropping out of school. The reasons for this include poverty, early marriage, lack of access to basic facilities like toilets, gender discrimination, and safety concerns. This has significant implications for India's economic development and social welfare.

Also Read: 5 Reasons Why School Infrastructure Is Important for A Child's Growth

The State of Education in India

Despite significant progress in recent years, education remains a challenge in India. According to a report by the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO), the dropout rate for girls in India is higher than that for boys, particularly in rural areas. In the 2017-2018 academic year, the dropout rate for girls was

4.1%, compared to 3.4% for boys. The report also found that the highest dropout rate was in the age group of 15-16 years.

However, the All India Survey on Higher Education (AISHE) 2020-2021, released by the Ministry of Education, shows that female enrolments have increased from 1.88 crores in 2019-20 to 2.01 crores in 2020-21, indicating an increase of approximately 44 lakh (28%) since 2014-15. The percentage of female enrolments to total enrolments has also risen from 45% in 2014-15 to nearly 49% in 2020-21. While there has been an increase in enrolment for girls in recent years, there are still many critical areas to be covered in the future.[5,7,8]

Reasons for Female School Dropouts in India

There are several reasons why girls drop out of school in India. One of the primary reasons is poverty, as many families cannot afford to send their daughters to school due to financial constraints. Another reason is the need for more infrastructure and basic amenities in schools. Many schools lack proper toilet facilities, which makes it challenging for girls to attend school regularly. Additionally, social and cultural factors play a significant role in female school dropouts. Early marriage, gender discrimination, and the expectation of domestic duties are some reasons why girls drop out of school.

Economic Impact on Female School Dropouts

The economic and social impact of female school dropouts is considerable, both at an individual and societal level. From a personal perspective, dropping out of school can severely limit a girl's employment opportunities and earning potential. According to a World Bank study, every additional year of schooling for a girl increases her earning potential by 10-20%. By dropping out of school early, girls are depriving themselves of the opportunity to earn higher wages and enjoy better economic prospects.

From a societal perspective, the economic impact of female school dropouts can be equally significant. A lack of educated women in the workforce can lead to a skills gap and a loss of productivity, harming economic growth and development. A study by the McKinsey Global Institute estimated that if women in India participated in the workforce at the same rate as men, it could add \$2.9 trillion to the country's GDP by 2025.

Social Impact of Female School Dropouts

Moreover, the social impact of female school dropouts is significant. Girls who drop out of school early are often more vulnerable to poverty, exploitation, and other forms of discrimination. They are also less likely to be aware of their rights and less equipped to advocate for themselves, perpetuating a cycle of poverty and disadvantage.

Education is essential for promoting gender equality and empowering women. By depriving girls of education, we are limiting their ability to participate in society and exercise their rights fully, leading to higher levels of gender-based violence, lower levels of political participation, and other forms of inequality.

DISCUSSION

Solutions to Address Female School Dropouts in India

Several solutions can be implemented to address the issue of female school dropouts in India. One of the most effective solutions is to provide financial incentives to families to send their daughters to school. The government can provide cash transfers or scholarships to cover the cost of education. Additionally, improving the infrastructure and basic amenities in schools can help reduce dropouts. Schools should have proper toilet facilities, safe drinking water, and adequate classroom space to accommodate all students. Finally, addressing social and cultural factors contributing to female school

dropouts is crucial. Raising awareness about the importance of education and promoting gender equality can help address these factors. The female school dropouts significantly affect India's economic development and social welfare. Urgent and coordinated efforts are required from the government and civil society organizations to address the issue. Improving the quality of education, providing safe and secure schooling facilities, addressing gender-based discrimination, and promoting policies that encourage female education are some of the measures that can be taken. By addressing this issue, India can take a significant step towards achieving gender equality, enhancing economic growth, and ensuring social welfare for all its citizens.

Early marriages and chores at home are key reasons why girls drop out of school, The National Family Health Survey-5 (2019-21) indicates. Of the over 21,800 girls who had dropped out of school before the 2019-20 school year, just over 13% girls did so as they were required for house work and almost 7% did so as they were married off even though child marriage is illegal. When it comes to paid work, the percentage of boys who dropped out for work is higher when compared to girls. A total of 21,851 girls and 20,084 boys had dropped out of school before the 2019-20 school year. The survey draws out the main reasons for children (6-17 age group) for dropping out of school in that school year. The urban and rural break-up shows that of the total girls, 17,786 were from rural areas and 4,065 from urban. Among boys 14,933 were from rural areas and 5,152 from urban settlements. The reasons reflect the gender divide and how patriarchy and economic factors were critical in making children and teenagers vulnerable to ending up as school dropouts. While the percentage of girls who dropped out of school to assist with house work was just over 13%, it was close to 10% for boys. On the other hand, when it came to children dropping out as they were required for outside work for payment in cash or kind, nearly 6% boys fell in in this category while girls accounted for 2.5%. [9,10,11]

Also more boys (4.3%) dropped out of school as they were required for work on the farm or family business compared to girls (2.3%).

Underage marriage was the cause for almost 7% girls dropping out whereas for boys this percentage was 0.3%. At least 2% girls dropped out due to safety concerns at school and 1.7% did so as there were no proper school facilities for girls.

The data shows that cost of education figures as a crucial factor. Nearly 21% girls dropped out for the reason that education costs too much. This percentage was 16% for boys. While cost of education appears to be a bigger concern for girls than boys, a significantly higher (35.7%) number of boys dropped out due to lack of interest in studies as compared to the girls (21.4%) who also gave up on their education for the same reason. Just over 6% girls dropped out as school was too far from home. Meanwhile, in the section on schooling, NFHS-5 shows that during survey it came through that overall, 72% of females and 87% of males age six and over have ever attended school. Educational attainment at the household level increased between 2015-16 and 2019-21. Among females, the median number of years of schooling increased from 4.4 years to 4.9 years and for males from 6.9 years to 7.3 years. Over the same period, the percentage of females and males with no schooling decreased from 31% of females and 15% of males to 28% of females and 14% of males.

RESULTS

A U-Report poll of the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) conducted in India on International Women's Day 2022 revealed that around 38% of the respondents knew at least one female student who had dropped out of school. The report by UNICEF India suggests that the increase in the dropout rate of girls from schools across the country is alarming. With the number of COVID-19 cases on a decline, schools in India have resumed offline functioning. However, the multiple re-opening and closures of schools in the past two years had caused massive disruptions in the education of crores of schoolchildren.

It is reported that at the peak of the pandemic, around 24.7 crore schoolchildren were affected due to the closure. The digital divide in the country posed a problem for children who could not access remote learning when schools were closed. Children from low-income homes suffered the most as they faced the most difficulty in accessing remote learning. The 2020-21 report by Unified District Information System for Education Plus (UDISE+) revealed that the annual dropout rate of secondary school students was 14.6%.

Yasumasa Kimura, UNICEF India Representative, fears that there is a risk of a “lost generation of children” who will never return to school and that the impact on female students is disproportionately worse.

“This is indeed a matter of grave concern. It is critical that we work towards transitioning all children back into learning. UNICEF is supporting the Government of India in back-to-school campaigns, awareness and outreach initiatives and learning recovery programmes at schools and in the communities. We must not only bring children back to school but also focus on putting strong remedial learning initiatives in place to ensure retention and continuity of learning,” added Kimura.

UNICEF is a body of the United Nations that works to reach the most disadvantaged children and protect their rights in over 190 countries and territories. In 2021, UNICEF India supported the government and partnering bodies in 17 states to provide technology that allowed 1.55 crore children, of which 50.5% were female, to continue learning from home.

UNICEF India also contributed to the efforts of the Union education ministry’s plans of reopening schools in 2022.[12,13,15]

CONCLUSIONS

Gujarat, Bihar, Karnataka, Assam and Punjab are among seven states where the school dropout rate at the secondary level was higher than the national average of 12.6 per cent in 2021-22, according to official data. This information was collated from the minutes of the Project Approval Board (PAB) meetings held under the Ministry of Education to discuss the implementation of the "Samagra Shiksha" programme for 2023. The meetings with states and union territories took place between March and May this year.[17,18]

The government views dropout as a barrier to achieving the new National Education Policy's aim of 100 per cent Gross Enrolment Rate (GER) at the school level by future, according to officials. The details of the PAB meeting minutes show that the dropout rate at the secondary level in 2021-22 was 20.46 per cent in Bihar, 17.85 per cent in Gujarat, 20.3 per cent in Assam, 16.7 per cent in Andhra Pradesh, 17.2 per cent in Punjab, 21.7 per cent in Meghalaya and 14.6 per cent in Karnataka.[19]

REFERENCES

1. Усамов, И.П. (2019-12-18). "Digital Transformation of Education: Challenges and Prospects". Вестник ГГНТУ. Гуманитарные и социально-экономические науки. 3 (17). doi:10.34708/gstou.2019.17.3.021. ISSN 2686-9721. S2CID 242230851.
2. ^ Osler, Audrey; Vincent, Kerry (2003 - 12-16). Girls and Exclusion. doi:10.4324/9780203465202. ISBN 9781134412839.
3. ^ Osman, Abdal Monium Khidir (November 2002). "Challenges for integrating gender into poverty alleviation programmes: Lessons from Sudan". Gender & Development. 10 (3): 22–30. doi:10.1080/13552070215922. ISSN 1355-2074. S2CID 71270250.
4. ^ Dekkers, Hetty P.J.M.; Bosker, Roel J.; Driessen, Geert W.J.M. (March 2000). "Complex Inequalities of Educational Opportunities. A Large-Scale Longitudinal Study on the Relation Between Gender, Social Class, Ethnicity and School Success". Educational Research and

- Evaluation. 6 (1):59–82. doi:10.1076/1380-3611(200003)6:1;1-i;ft059. ISSN 1380-3611. S2CID 144400482.
5. ^{a b} Cracking the code: girls' and women's education in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM). Paris: UNESCO. 2017. ISBN 9789231002335.
 6. ^a "Historical summary of faculty, students, degrees, and finances in degree-granting institutions: Selected years, 1869-70 through 2005-06". Nces.ed.gov. Retrieved 2014-08-22.
 7. ^a "CAMFED USA: What we do". CAMFED. Archived from the original on October 9, 2011. Retrieved October 11, 2011.
 8. ^a "Girls Education:A lifeline to development". 1995. Archived from the original on 2021-04-25. Retrieved 2022-02-03.
 9. ^a Filmer, Deon (2007-06-29). "If you build it, will they come? School availability and school enrolment in 21 poor countries". *The Journal of Development Studies*. 43 (5): 901–928. doi:10.1080/00220380701384588. ISSN 0022-0388. S2CID 216140496.
 10. ^a Herz, Barbara; Subbarao, K.; Habib, Masooma; Raney, Laura (1991-09-30). "Letting girls learn". *World Bank Discussion Papers*. doi:10.1596/0-8213-1937-x. ISBN 978-0-8213-1937-6. ISSN 0259-210X.
 11. ^a Paudel, Ramesh C. (2019-12-31). "Collier, P. (2008). *The Bottom Billion: Why the Poorest Countries are Failing and What Can be Done About It*, Oxford University Press, USA". *Economic Journal of Nepal*. 42 (3–4): 79–82. doi:10.3126/ejon.v42i3-4.36039. ISSN 1018-631X. S2CID 242154293.
 12. ^a "What Have We Learned About Moral Courage in Organizations?", *Moral Courage in Organizations: Doing the Right Thing at Work*, Routledge, pp. 235–240, 2015-03-26, doi:10.4324/9781315702285-28, ISBN 978-1-315-70228-5, retrieved 2023-03-25
 13. ^{a b} Grimm, Wolfram (November 2006). "What Is Evidence-Based, What Is New in Medical Therapy of Acute Heart Failure?". *Herz Kardiovaskuläre Erkrankungen*. 31 (8): 771–779. doi:10.1007/s00059-006-2910-y. ISSN 0340-9937. PMID 17149679. S2CID 38811473.
 14. ^a "Plan Overseas - Why Girls?". Plan Canada. Archived from the original on November 13, 2011. Retrieved October 29, 2011.
 15. ^a "Plan Overseas - Education Girl-friendly schools see enrollment rates soar in Burkina Faso". Plan Canada. Archived from the original on October 11, 2011. Retrieved October 29, 2011.
 16. ^a Chandra, Anjani; Martinez, Gladys M.; Mosher, William D.; Abma, Joyce C.; Jones, Jo (2005). "Fertility, family planning, and reproductive health of U.S. women: Data from the 2002 National Survey of Family Growth". *PsycEXTRA Dataset*. doi:10.1037/e414702008-001. Retrieved 2023-03-25.
 17. ^a "Kakkar, Baron, (Ajay Kumar Kakkar) (born 28 April 1964)", *Who's Who*, Oxford University Press, 2010-12-01, doi:10.1093/ww/9780199540884.013.u251313, retrieved 2023-03-25
 18. ^a Ross, Catherine E.; Mirowsky, John; Goldsteen, Karen (November 1990). "The Impact of the Family on Health: The Decade in Review". *Journal of Marriage and the Family*. 52 (4): 1059. doi:10.2307/353319. ISSN 0022-2445. JSTOR 353319.
 19. ^a Miller, Brent C.; Moore, Kristin A. (November 1990). "Adolescent Sexual Behavior, Pregnancy, and Parenting: Research through the 1980s". *Journal of Marriage and the Family*. 52 (4): 1025. doi:10.2307/353317. ISSN 0022-2445. JSTOR 353317.